

ACCOUNTABILITY AND TRANSPARENCY IN TAX ADMINISTRATION

Adesemowo Modupeola M.¹ & Falaye Ibukun²

¹Department of Accounting & Finance, Chrisland University Abeokuta Ogun State

²Department of Accounting, Joseph Ayo Babalola University Arakeji Osun State

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15106699>

Abstract

To enhance confidence and trust, tax officials ought to openly be accountable for their actions within a framework of responsibility to the society it operates. A lack of reliable assessment framework made it difficult to measure their performance and therefore are perceived in the view of the public as corrupt and not trustworthy of managing public resources. This study examines the effect of tax administration on accountability and transparency of tax officers. The study included a survey of 2956 professional and executive cadre officers in State Internal Revenue Service in Lagos, Ogun and Oyo States as at 2022. Using regression analysis, this study shows that tax administration significantly affects the accountability and transparency of tax officers. The State tax authority should ensure that members of staff are accountable for tax resources collected, should also ensure to make available their reports in a transparent manner.

Keywords: Accountability and transparency, tax administration, tax assessment, tax collection and tax remittance

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian economy is in dire need of revenue to recover from the multiple recessions it has been subjected to in the past few years and from the recent pandemic caused by COVID-19. This need accentuates the eagerness on the part of States government in Nigeria to look for new sources of fund or become aggressive and innovative in the approach of collecting revenue even from exiting sources (Atuguba, (2021); Indrawan (2021) & Fasoye, (2020) and because the federal allocation to States has reduced (Adegbie, Nwaobia, & Osinowo, 2020). The prevailing trend in Nigeria towards revenue generation is the constant increase in taxes and multiplicity of taxes which is causing a great burden on the citizens of the country, it is like an analogy that says when water is poured into a basket and the basket cannot retain the water the solution is not to pour in more water but to look into the basket and block the leakage. The most common leakage or challenge to revenue mobilization which has been popularly researched is tax evasion and tax avoidance, others are tax compliance, multiplicity of taxes (Akinleye, Olaoye, & Ogunmakin, 2019; Lipniewicz, 2017) all which are tax issues in respect of the taxpayer and their effects on tax revenue generation but not much research work has been done in respect of tax revenue agencies and their officers who are the managers of the taxes paid by the taxpayers to the government and the impact of their performance outcome on tax revenue generation at State levels.

The tax system in Nigeria continuously faces diverse challenges while tax authorities operate under suboptimal conditions. The challenge of tax authorities' sub-optimality and inability to generate

non-oil tax revenue to meet the State's recurrent and capital operations is perturbing. The World Bank Ease of Doing Business (2020) report ranks Nigeria as taking 159th position out of 190 World economies in Africa, the ranking is based on indicators such as ease of paying taxes, total tax rate, time to comply, number of payments and post filling index. The cost of tax collection is about 4% as against the international benchmark of 1%, this indicates the use of enforced compliance and the use of external consultants.

Efficient and effective tax revenue agencies would be strategic and respond swiftly to changes in their environment. There are so many challenges confronting State Internal Revenue Service as revenue authorities in their various jurisdictions which hinder their effectiveness and efficiencies (Salman, Akintayo, Kasum, and Bamigbade, 2019; Kasum, Sanni and Fagbemi, 2019). Assessing and qualifying the strength of tax authorities has generally proven to be less straightforward (OECD, 2014). The main reason for the scarcity of available work in this area is mostly related to the lack of a reliable framework or appropriate assessment tool to measure the impact of tax agency functions in its various jurisdictions and that can also help to indicate and improve lapses (IMF, 2015). Generating revenue through taxes has always been a challenge to all governments at their various levels (Osho, Ajayi, and Ogunbodede, 2019), moreover the challenge of raising revenue is compounded by the lack or inadequate ability of government to identify and properly evaluate the performance outcomes of revenue authorities that would enhance revenue generation.

There are few tools available for revenue agencies to evaluate their performance and especially the performance outcome of their officers and activities for effectiveness and efficiency. Some of these tools include the 1999 Fiscal Blueprint of the EU, Public Expenditure and Financial Accountability (PEFA) assessment tool, the OECD 15 indicators for assessing key cross country organizational and operational aspects of revenue administration relative to international best practices, and several indexes formulated by various researchers in their works (Criveil, 2019; IMF, 2013, 2019; OECD, 2015). Some or most of these tools usually considers specific aspects of performance indicators, not so many of these tools have a comprehensive overview of the performance indicators.

The Tax Administration Diagnostic Assessment Tool (TADAT, 2019) is a means to provide an objective and standardized assessment of the relative strengths and weaknesses of a tax agency addressing questions of what and why with respect to performance. It is an integrated monitoring framework that measures performance of a tax agency at a point in time. It is designed to provide objective and consistent assessments of the performance outcome of tax agency' essential functions (Dabla-Norris, Misch, Cleary, and Khwaja, 2019). TADAT which is an initiative of IMF, (2013), identifies nine performance outcome areas (integrity of registered taxpayers, risk management, voluntary compliance, timely tax filling of declarations, timely payment of taxes, accurate reporting, tax dispute resolution, revenue management and accountability and transparency) that are indicators of the strengths and weakness of a tax agency. According to IMF, TADAT initiative is part of a wider agenda of the international community to help tax authorities strengthen their tax systems and to better mobilize the domestic revenue they need to provide essential goods and services to their citizens in a sustainable and economical way.

This study intends to adapt the TADAT to assess the performance outcome area in terms of accountability and transparency for State Internal Revenue in South-West Nigeria. The study therefore examines the effect of tax administration on accountability and transparency of State Internal Revenue in South-West Nigeria.

Figure 1: POAS
Source: TADAT (2019) Adapted

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Transparency and Accountability

Accountability and transparency were first conceptually analyzed together in studies by Fox (2007), Hood (2010) and Meijer (2014), the authors assert that the relationship between the concepts is more complex than expected. The two concepts, widely studied individually by prominent scholars, are most often used as synonyms. According to Lane (2012) accountability is giving account of actions and decisions, where A is accountable to B when A is obliged to inform B about A's (past or future) actions and decisions, to justify them, and to suffer punishment in the case of eventual misconduct. According to Mabillard and Zumofen (2017), accountability is an important part of a public manager's job. In the public sector, Végh (2018), attested that accountability comprises regular reporting requirements to the government and the parliament, and an oversight function by external audit. Reporting requirements usually include the publication of an annual plan and an annual report. According to Olugbusi and Ojo (2021), the reporting system in government has been criticized for not giving an accurate account for resources under its control, which is evidenced with various reoccurring cases of misappropriation of funds and assets, fraud and corruption among government employees. Jashari and Pepaj (2018) described transparency to mean being open, communicative, and responsive about actions and decisions. Transparency is the quality of being easily seen through and, in governance, it is when actions of public servants and entities are scrupulous enough to bear public scrutiny. Transparency enables citizens to monitor the work of the public administration in general as well as the decision-making process specifically. Hadush, (2020) defined transparency as public access to knowledge of the policies and strategies of government. It is the free flow of information which can be enhanced through the improvement of democratic process.

Based on some empirical studies such as, (Mabillard & Zumofen, 2017; Hood 2010; Meijer (2014), the studies established a link between the principle of accountability and transparency, that through

transparency, public officials corroborate that the principle of accountability and responsibility is respected. Tax officials as managers of revenue generating agencies that practices transparency by accounting or seen to be accountable for all tax revenue generated as resources at their disposal are considered good stewards who deserve more responsibility and trust (Olugbusi & Ojo, 2021). Their institutionalization reflects the principle that tax authorities should be answerable for the way they use public resources and exercise authority in order to enhance society’s confidence and trust (Mabillard & Zumofen, 2017).

2.2 Concept of tax administration

According to Fasoye, (2020); Omodero and Dandago, (2019, tax is the most important and reliable source of government revenue, accounting for ninety percent or more of the total income accruing to the modern-day government, also Taddesse, (2022) asserted that the government is assured at all times of the certainty and consistency of generating revenue from tax through the inherent power of the government to impose taxes. Taxation as a means of raising government revenue is a key ingredient in the social contract between the citizens and the government of a country and thus a burden bore by taxpayers, revenue agencies and the government (Begim, 2018). According to Atuguba, (2021); Indrawan (2021); taxation is an indispensable instrument for measuring civilization and funding national development and growth in most societies and nations of the world.

Tax administration is the process of assessing and collecting taxes from individuals and companies by relevant tax authorizes, in such a way that current amount assessed is collected efficiently and effectively with minimum tax avoidance or tax evasion. The National Tax Policy (NTP, 2012; 2017) is the framework for reforming tax system in Nigeria. The document is the basis for tax administration in Nigeria Tax administration is the power enable available to tax agencies to collect tax. There is a growing global interest in improving the ability of tax administration of countries in the developing economy to collect domestic tax revenue (Coplin, & Nwafor, 2019; IMF, 2011). According to Arif and Rawat (2018), a strong system of tax administration has an effective impact on revenue generation. According to Hardika, Sukayasa, and Yintayani (2018), a modern tax administration system should be seen to have improved or striving towards excellence of its core administrative functions of assessment, collection and remittance of local taxes by revenue agencies. According to Brondolo and Zhang (2016); Lewis (2016), tax administration helps to boost tax revenue and also various tax administration reforms has helped to build and improve taxpayers’ perception of the tax system over the years. The strength of tax administration in many emerging countries scores particularly well when considering their relative level of development and the effect on revenue mobilization. The ability of tax agencies to generate significant revenue depend on the efficiency and effectiveness of tax administration (Morenike, Samuel, & Festus 2022).

Table 1: Benefits of an Improved Tax Administration

Benefit	Specific Gains for Domestic Resource Mobilization
---------	---

Greater potential for revenue mobilization	Return on investment in additional tax revenue is several times the cost of the new system. Sustainable support is provided for administrative systems and revenue growth.
Efficiency	Greater efficiency across all functions, including those with direct relevance to increasing domestic revenue mobilization: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enhanced risk management for better audit case selection • better ability to detect fraudulent tax refunds • ability for the tax authority to view the taxpayer in an integrated way across all tax types • reduction in taxpayer compliance costs and agency costs
Transparency	Unique user identification with attached audit log of transactions ensures accountability. Use of discretionary powers must be within parameters that the system can monitor. Documents are stored on system electronically and provide an evidentiary record. Internal control systems contain alerts when unusual behavior by an individual is detected.
Governance	Improved management information reporting assists management decision-making.

Source: Tansey (2019)

3. Hypothesis development

3.1 Tax Administration and Accountability and Transparency

The Nigerian tax system is one that has been solely dependent on one aspect of administering taxes which is on the oil sector (Adegbe, Nwaobia, and Osinowo, 2020), not until recently that the fall in oil prices brought about the need for the government and the those charged with the responsibility of administering taxes to look into the non-oil sector to generate revenue and these has not been easy for the tax revenue agencies. The inability of the oil sector to continue to finance the country revealed the inefficiency and ineffectiveness of the State Internal Revenue Authorities (Egwaikhide, 2019). According to Assefa (2013), developing nations like Nigeria need tax authorities that would respond swiftly and avert the downturn in the economy, who are proactive to increase the number of taxpayers in the nonoil sector thereby closing the tax gap.

According to Sciso (2017), transparency is a practical result of public servants' duty of accounting for their actions and decisions regarding resources entrusted in their care, the author therefore concludes that accountability and transparency are key values for responsible government representative as being open brings about efficiency and credibility of government endeavours. According to Ogundajo, Oyedokun and Ajibade (2019), some government agencies and their officials fail to render account of their stewardship, which made it difficult to measure their performance and therefore are perceived in the view of the public as corrupt and not trustworthy of managing public resources. Accountability and transparency improve the performance of public

agencies, as accountability and transparency must be a push factor towards gaining the trust of the public while a low degree of accountability and transparency creates opportunity for corruption by tax officials.

Van den Boogaard, Prichard, Beach and Mohiuddin (2020), in their study conducted in Ghana and Sierra Leone, found out that taxpayers beyond the basic tax information are interested in how much revenue is enough for collection and how the revenue collected has been put to use by the government through a two way communication via dialogue and other forms of public interactions, moreover the authors found out that tax transparency is more meaningful to taxpayers if it is accessible (Hadush, 2020) and clearly understood in their tax dealings. Adekoya, Enyi and Akintoye (2019), in their study conducted in Lagos, Ogun and Oyo States found out that accountability positively affects taxpayer's voluntary compliance and also that the government makes tax collection information and its usage available promptly and timely to its citizens. Augustine and Rufus (2019), found out in their study that transparency of government in collection and utilization of taxes fosters taxpayers to have trust in the government which significantly increases revenue generation. Tax officials as managers of revenue generating agencies that practice transparency by accounting or seen to be accountable for all tax revenue generated as resources at their disposal are considered good stewards who deserve more responsibility and trust (Olugbusi & Ojo, 2021).

H1= Tax administration through tax assessment, tax collection and tax remittance has a significant effect on accountability and transparency.

1. METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted in this study is the survey research design. The target population, who were respondents of the study were 2956 professional and executive cadre officers in State Internal Revenue Service in Lagos, Ogun and Oyo States as at 2022 directly responsible for the assessment, collection and remittance of taxes, purposive sampling technique was employed in selecting the South -West geopolitical zone considered for the study because three States (Lagos, Ogun and Oyo) were among the top five States that generated the highest revenue in Nigeria (ASVI, 2020, 2022) and the states in this region has common demographic characteristics, common language, and cultural norms and basically has the same informal sectors and individual taxpayers setting (Enyi, Akintoye & Adekoya, 2019; Oyebamiji, 2018). Simple random samples were employed to select the respondents. The sample size of the study was determined using Taro Yamane formula. The formula derived a sample size of 352 respondents, and a modification upward of 10% of the sample size was added to take care of possible nonresponse (Asika, 2009), thereby increasing total sample size to 387. A total of 382 (98.7%) questionnaires were correctly filled in and returned by the respondents while only 1.3% of the respondents did not return the questionnaire. The questions appraised in the questionnaire were restructured to reflect Nigerian characteristics and was modified based on the work of TADAT (IMF, 2013; Akol, Magumba, Loke, Nalukwago & Barugahara, 2020; Dabla-Norris, Misch, Cleary & Khwaja, 2020; Ligomeka, 2019). The research instrument, a well-structured close ended questionnaire and scaled using a Six (6) point Likert scale which was converted into code manuals of (Strongly Agree = 6, Agree

= 5, Partially Agree = 4, Partially Disagree = 3, Disagree =2, Strongly Disagree = 1) used for the study was validated, certified by experts in subject matter and versatile in research. The study employed the Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin's (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. The KMO of 0.577, 0.511, 0.507 and 0.544 for accountability and transparency, tax assessment, tax collection and remittances respectively are greater than 50%, the decision rule is that if KMO is greater than 0.5, the item(s) actually measured the variables in the study. The Bartlett test of Sphericity at 0.048, 0.000, 0.010 and 0.040 for accountability and transparency, tax assessment, tax collection and remittances respectively, which was less than 5%, indicated a highly significant relationship among the variables in measuring the variables under study. In this study, the KMO test is greater than 50%, and the Bartlett test of Sphericity result is less than 5%, indicating that the questionnaire items for each construct measured what was intended. In order to determine the internal consistency reliability of each variable, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was applied at 0.850, 0.858, 0.908 and 0.742 for accountability and transparency, tax assessment, tax collection and remittances respectively, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for all the variables in the study is above 0.70 threshold for Cronbach's alpha, this indicates that the instrument used for evaluation was highly reliable.

The model specification, $Y = f(X)$

Where Y = Accountability and Transparency (ACT) (dependent variable)

X = Tax Administration (TAD) (Independent variable)

x1 = Tax Assessment (TASS)

x2 = Tax Collection (TCOL)

x3 = Tax Remittance (TREM)

$$ACT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TASS + \beta_2 TCOL + \beta_3 TREM + \epsilon_i \text{ -----Model}$$

It is expected that a positive relationship would exist between tax Administration and accountability and transparency of selected State Internal Revenue Service in Nigeria. Thus, $\beta_1 > 0$.

Table 2: Total Number of Sample Frame

State	Lagos	Ogun	Oyo	Total
Number of professional and executive officers Cadre	2390	439	127	2956

Source: Researcher's Field study (2022)

2. ANALYSIS

Table 3: Demographic Analyses of Respondents

Respondents Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender:		
Male	229	59.9
Female	141	36.9
Others	12	3.1
	382	100
Age:		
18-27	46	12.0
28-37	104	27.2
38-47	183	47.9
48 above	49	12.8
	382	100
Length of years:		
1-5 years	98	25.7
6-15 years	212	55.5
16-25 years	63	16.5
26 years above	9	2.4
	382	100
Academic qualification:		
HND	111	29
BSc	120	31.4
MBA	121	31.7
MSc	28	7.3
PHD	1	0.3
Missing	1	0.3
	382	100
Professional qualification:		
ICAN	130	34.1
ANAN	43	11.3
CITN	146	38.2
Others	63	16.5
	382	100
Work section:		
Assessment	248	65
Collection	114	29.8
Remittance	17	4.5
Missing	3	0.8
	382	100

Source: Researcher's Field study (2022)

Table 3 shows that out of the 382 respondents, 229 were male while 141 were female and 12 represents others that did not indicate their gender. This shows that 59.9% of the respondents are male while 36.9% are female and 3.1% represent others. Thus, more male participated in the survey than female. This implies that the tax agencies have higher number of male members of staff than the female members of staff.

Table 3 shows that 12% of the respondents were within the age range of 18-27 years, 27.2% of the respondents were within the age range of 28-37, 47.9% of the respondents were within the range of 38-47 while 12.8% of the respondents were above 48 years. This indicates that majority of the respondents were between the age bracket of 28-37 and 38-47. Thus, the respondents were considered to be matured in age to give reliable information. The table also depicts that 98 or 25.7% of the respondents have spent less than 5 years with the agencies, 121 or 55.5% of the respondents have spent between 6-15 years, 63 or 16.5% of the respondents have spent between 16-25 years while 9 or 2.4% represents the respondents that have spent over 26 years with the agencies. This shows that a combination of respondents between 6-15 years and less than 5 years represents are more in number than others in the sampled agencies. This means that a greater number of the members of staff in the sampled agencies have spent between 6-15 years in service at the agencies.

Table 3 shows that 111 or 29% of the respondents had HND, 120 or 31.4% of the respondents had a B.Sc., 121 or 31.7% had MBA, 28 or 7.3% had M.Sc., while only 1 or 0.3% had a PhD and 1 or 0.3% did not indicate academic qualification. This shows that the respondents have a good academic background that can ensure reliable knowledge about the topic of study. The table also shows that 130 or 34.1% of the respondents are members of ICAN, 43 or 11.3% of the respondents had ANNA qualification, 146 or 38.2% of the respondents had CITN certificate while only 63 or 16.5% had other forms of qualification not required for this study. This indicates that most of the respondents are professionals in the field of accounting and taxation which implies that they have a vast knowledge of the study. The table shows that 65% or 248 of the respondents were officers who worked in the assessment section, 29.8% or 114 worked in the collection section while 4.5% or 17 worked in the remittance section and only 3 or 0.8% of the respondents did not indicate their work section. This indicates that majority of the respondents worked in the assessment section, therefore more staff are involved in assessment of taxpayer's declarations, which implies that the sampled agencies are more focused in assessment of income tax than tax collection and remittance.

Table 4: Respondents Responses on Accountability and Transparency (ACT)

Accountability and Transparency (ACT)	Mean	SDV
ACT 1	5.23	1.08
ACT 2	5.23	1.05
ACT 3	4.99	1.18
ACT 4	4.82	1.73

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The mean values of a range of 4.82 to 5.23 indicates on the average that the respondents agree to tax administration having a significant effect on accountability and transparency in Lagos, Ogun and Oyo State Internal Revenue Service in Nigeria.

Table 5: Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
(Constant)	3.160	0.259	12.191	0.001

TASS	0.135	0.035	3.820	0.001
TCL	0.051	0.030	1.682	0.093
TREM	0.188	0.045	4.187	0.001
R-squared	0.133			
Adjusted R²	0.126			
F-Statistics	19.340			
Prob(F-Stat)	0.001			
Observation	382			

Dependent Variable: ACT; Obs.: 382

***significant at 5%**

$$ACT = \beta_0i + \beta_1TASSi + \beta_2TCOLi + \beta_3TREMi + \epsilon_i \text{ -----Model}$$

$$ACT = 3.160 + 0.135TASS + 0.051TCOL + 0.188TREM + \epsilon_i$$

3. DISCUSSION

The table 4 represents the regression hypothesis testing the effect of tax administration on accountability and transparency of taxpayers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria. The result indicates that Tax assessment (TASS), Tax collection (TCOL) and Tax remittance (TREM) all have a positive effect on accountability and transparency of taxpayers in South-West Nigeria. This is indicated by the parameters of the coefficients which are $\beta_1=0.135$, $\beta_2 =0.051$ and $\beta_3=0.188$. This is consistent with a prior expectation of the study which states that tax administration would exert a positive effect on accountability and transparency of taxpayers in South-West Nigeria. This implies that one percent increase in TASS would lead to 13.5% increase in accountability and transparency of taxpayers, also one percent increase in TCOL would result to an increase in accountability and transparency of taxpayers by 5.1%, while one percent increase in TREM would give 18.8% increase in accountability and transparency of taxpayers. TASS is significant at t-statistics of 3.820 and p-value of $0.001 < 0.005$, TCOL is also significant at t-statistics of 1.682 and p-value of $0.093 > 0.005$, while TREM is significant at t-statistics of 4.187 with a p-value of $0.001 < 0.005$.

The direction of the coefficient implies that improvement in the effort to better tax Assessment, tax collection and tax Remittance would bring about increase in accountability and transparency of taxpayers in South-West Nigeria. Furthermore, when the value of probability of t-stat is considered which assess the significance of each variable, the result showed that tax assessment, tax collection and tax remittance significantly affect accountability and transparency of tax officers in South-West Nigeria.

The adjusted R² which is the coefficient of determination is 0.126 (12.6%), this indicates that only 13% variation in the accountability and transparency of taxpayers in South-West Nigeria can be explained by tax administration proxied by tax assessment, tax remittance and tax collection while the remaining 87.4 % is caused by other variables not captured in the model. This is a moderate

effect and evidence of causality. The result is further confirmed by the probability of the F-statistics which measured the effect of the model. The probability stood at 0.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance adopted for this study.

At the 0.05 level of significance, the F-statistics is 19.34, where the p-value of the F-statistics is 0.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance adopted for this study. This implies that null hypothesis which states that tax administration does not have significant effect on the accountability and transparency of taxpayers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria was not accepted. Therefore, from the regression estimates, tax administration measured significantly affects the accountability and transparency of tax officers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria.

The result of the hypotheses predicts a positive and significant relationship between Tax administration significantly affects accountability and transparency of taxpayers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that there is significant relationship between tax administration as it significantly affects accountability and transparency of taxpayers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria.

The findings of this study is in tandem with the work of Van den Boogaard, Prichard, Beach and Mohiuddin (2020), in their study conducted in Ghana and Sierra Leone, found out that tax administration has a significant effect on accountability and transparency. The study further found out that tax compliance demands tax authorities to exhibit tax transparency about their stewardship role, open communication and trustworthy in handling tax revenue. Augustine and Rufus (2019), found out in their study that transparency of government in collection and utilization of taxes fosters taxpayers to have trust in the government which significantly increases revenue generation, also a study by Siahaan (2013), confirms that for transparency to have any impact on compliance of taxpayers in Indonesia it has to be through trust of the taxpayers in the government.

The findings of this study is not in tandem with Olugbusi and Ojo (2021), the authors found out that accountability and transparency has a significant but negative effect on revenue generation of State Internal Revenue service. This implies that poor accountability due to corruption and lack of financial information from the revenue agencies as stewards of government negatively affects tax revenue generation in Nigeria. Hadush (2020), the study found out that the Zalanbessa town revenue agency and its officials were not transparent in dealing with tax matters as decision regarding tax matters were not open to the general public and therefore there was no enabling environment for the public to voice their opinions on tax matters, the resulting effect is low revenue generation which depicts that the tax administration functions had no influence on the performance of the tax agency. Morenike, Chukwudi & Bello (2024).

There exist a significant relationship between tax administration and accountability and transparency of registered taxpayers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria at 0.001 level of significance therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between tax administration and accountability and transparency of taxpayers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria.

4. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The study concludes that tax administration measured as tax assessment, tax remittance and tax collection has a significant effect on the accountability and transparency of taxpayers of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria.

The study recommends that tax agencies should allow external oversight of its activities by use of independent audit out government control to enhance integrity of members of staff. Tax agencies should make available publication of the agencies' activities, results, plans and financial reports in a transparent manner.

5. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

The study was limited to South-West geopolitical zone in Nigeria. Further studies should be researched on other geopolitical zones in Nigeria

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, Adesemowo, M., M. methodology, Adesemowo, M., M.; software, Falaye I.; validation, Adesemowo M., M. and Falaye, I ; formal analysis, Adesemowo M., M. and Falaye, I ; investigation, Adesemowo M., M. and Falaye, I. resources, Adesemowo M., M. and Falaye, I ; data curation, Adesemowo M., M. and Falaye, I ; writing—original draft preparation, Adesemowo M., M.; writing—review and editing, Adesemowo M., M. and Falaye, I ; funding acquisition, Adesemowo M., M. and Falaye, I. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Adegbe, F., F., Nwaobia, A. N., & Osinowo, O. O. (2020). Non-oil tax revenue on economic growth and development in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(3).
- Akinleye, G., T., Olaoye, F. O., & Ogunmakin, A. A. (2019). Effect of tax identification number on revenue generation in South-West Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 11(9), 170-177.
- Akintoye, I., R & Tashie, G., A. (2013). The effect of tax compliance on economic growth and development in Nigeria. *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 11(2).
- Arif, I., & Rawat, A. S. (2018). Corruption, governance, and tax revenue: evidence from EAGLE countries. *Journal of Transnational Management*, 23(2-3), 119-133.
- Augustine, A. A., & Rufus, A. I. (2019). Government transparency moderated by trust in government and voluntary tax compliance behaviour in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, (7)8, 624-644.
- Atuguba, R. (2021). Tax Culture: Perspectives from an African State. *American Journal of Trade and Policy*, 8(1), 25-58.
- Begin, Ainur. 2018. How to retire like a soviet person: Informality, household finances, and kinship in financialized Kazakhstan. *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute*. 24(4), 767–785.

- Coplin, N., & Nwafor, A. (2019). It's not all about the money: Domestic revenue mobilization, reducing inequality and building trust with citizens. Oxfam briefing paper.
- Crivelli, E. (2019). A basic tool to assess tax administration strength in emerging Europe. *Economics of Transition and Institutional Change*, 27(2), 425-446.
- Dabla-Norris, E., Misch, F., Cleary, D., & Khwaja, M. (2020). The quality of tax administration and firm performance: evidence from developing countries. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 27(3), 514-551.
- Fakile, A. S., Adegbe, F. F., & Faboyede, O. S. (2014). Mobilizing domestic revenue for sustainable development in Africa. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 2(2), 91-108.
- Fasoye, K. (2020). Does internally generated revenue (igr) have the potential to enhance fiscal viability of state governments in Nigeria. *Noble International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 5(3), 40-49.
- Hadush, A. T. (2020). Assessing transparency practice in revenues and tax administration: The case of Zalanbessa Town administration, Gulomikada woreda, Eastern Zone of Tigray Region, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 7(1), 576-584.
- Hardika, N. S., Sukayasa, I. K., & Yintayani, N. N. (2018, May). The effect of administration system and tax reports on line on service quality and restaurant's tax-payer compliance in Badung Regency. In *Proceedings*, 1(1), 134-140.
- House, J., Mazar, N., & Robitaille, N. (2015). Increasing timely tax payment with implementation intentions: A field experiment. *Academy of Management Proceedings* 1, 15131).
- IMF (International Monetary Fund). (2015b). Current challenges in revenue mobilization: Improving tax compliance. *International Monetary Fund Policy Paper*, Washington, DC. Retrieved on 4th March 2020.
- IMF (International Monetary Fund). (2011). <https://www.imf.org/external/np/pp/eng/2011/030811.pdf>. Retrieved on 4th March 2020.
- IMF (International Monetary Fund). (2015a). 'Understanding revenue administration: An initial data analysis using the revenue administration fiscal information tool. *International Monetary Fund Fiscal Affairs Department Report*, Washington, DC. <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/dp/2015/fad1501.pdf>. Retrieved on 4th March 2020.
- IMF (International Monetary Fund). (2016). Effective government for stronger growth. Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern Europe Regional economic issues, Washington, DC. Retrieved on 4th March 2020.
- Indrawan, R. (2021). Effect of tax audit and tax collection on tax revenue. *International Journal of Science, Technology & Management*, 2(6), 2077-2085.
- Kasum, A. S., Sanni, A. K., & Fagbemi, T. O. (2019). Tax Revenue Generation by Nigerian States- An Empirical Study of Self-Assessment and Tax-Collection Contracting Systems in Kwara State. *Global Journal of Accounting*, 5(1), 27-36.
- Lane, M. (2012). The Moral Dimension of Corporate Accountability 1. In *Global Responsibilities* (pp. 229-250). Routledge.
- Lipniewicz, R. (2017). Tax administration and risk management in the digital age. *Information Systems in Management*, 6(1), 26-37.
- Mabillard, V., & Zumofen, R. (2017). The complex relationship between transparency and accountability: A synthesis and contribution to existing frameworks. *Public Policy and Administration*, 32(2), 110-129.

- Mansor, M. (2010). Performance management for a tax administration: Integrating organisational diagnosis to achieve systemic congruence. *J. Australasian Tax Tchrs. Ass'n*, 5, 137.
- Morenike, A. M., Samuel, D. O., & Festus, A. F. (2022). Tax administration and voluntary compliance: A study of selected state internal revenue service in south-west Nigeria. *EDITORIAL BOARD*.
- Morenike, A. M., Chukwudi, C. E., & Bello, W. O. (2024). Tax Administration and Timely Payments: A study of selected State Internal Revenue Service in South-West Nigeria. *PERSPEKTIF*, 13(1), 189-199.
- Olugbusi, O. M., & Ojo, O. (2021). Accountability and transparency in Inland Revenue Services of Lagos and Ogun State, Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Humanities*, 6(2), 17-26.
- Omodero, C. O., & Dandago, K. I. (2019). Tax revenue and public service delivery: evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 10(2), 82-91.
- Osho, A. E., Ajayi, D. A., & Ogunbodede, R. O. (2019). Taxation as a source of revenue generation in local governments, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* 10(6).
- Oyedokun, G., E. (2015). Relevance of tax audit and tax investigation in Nigeria. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2910322> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2910322>.
- Salman, R. T., Akintayo, S., Kasum, A. S., & Bamigbade, D. (2019). Effects of taxpayers' identification number on revenue generation in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law* 16, 106 – 117.
- Small, O., & Brown, L. (2020). Taxpayer service provision and tax compliance: Evidence for large taxpayers in Jamaica. *Public Finance Review*, 48(2), 250-277.
- Taddesse, S. (2022). *Taxation for Sustained Prosperity: Collaborative Tax Policy Setting & Administration*. Publish, Inc..
- Tansey, D. (2019). Tax administration information systems: concept, design, and implementation.
- Van den Boogaard, V., Prichard, W., Beach, R., & Mohiuddin, F. (2020). Strengthening tax-accountability links: Fiscal transparency and taxpayer engagement in Ghana and Sierra Leone.
- Végh, (2018). Tax administration good governance. *EC Tax Review*, 27(1)